

Kinetics of the microwave-accelerated corrosion of aluminium in sodium hydroxide solution

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Abstract : The present work is based on the effects of microwave heating and water bath heating on the corrosion rate of aluminium in sodium hydroxide solution. The kinetic laws of the aluminium corrosion process were explored using the weight-loss method with different concentrations of alkaline solution at different reaction temperatures. The kinetic parameters obtained under the two sets of conditions were compared. The kinetic laws were regardless of mode of heating. The rate constant and pre-exponential factor obtained in case of microwave heating were significantly greater. The apparent activation energy in case of microwave heating was smaller. It has been concluded that microwave radiation shortened the time required for corrosion.

Keywords : Microwave accelerated corrosion, kinetics.

Introduction

The UN recommendations on the transport of dangerous goods provide testing standards for identifying and classifying dangerous goods. These standards include the corrosion hazard test, which involves measuring the amount of mass lost during corrosion. The standard corrosion test used to evaluate the corrosive dangers posed by chemicals meant for transportation takes at least 168 h¹. This is very time-consuming and cannot meet the requirements of short-distance transportation. To ensure safety and shorten testing time, a new, faster method of detection was developed and evaluated. It can accelerate the corrosion process and improve detection efficiency. Currently, many workers have published reports on corrosion, but they have mainly focused on organic and inorganic inhibitors of corrosion of different metals in alkaline and acid solutions. These studies focused on controlling the corrosion process by controlling metal dissolution and consumption²⁻⁷. A few studies have been made on the accelerated corrosion test methods to evaluate the performance of coatings and the service life of certain materials⁸⁻¹². Although the value of accelerating corrosion has been known for decades, there is scant literature on the tests for the purpose of evaluating corrosion hazards. Research on relative acceleration and corrosion ki-

netics is also very scarce. In the present study, a microwave heating method as also the traditional water bath heating method was followed to investigate the effects of microwaves on the corrosion rate. Aluminium sheets were allowed to corrode in sodium hydroxide solutions and the rates at which the aluminum corroded in the two processes were compared. The relevant kinetic parameters were determined. These test results provide important reference materials.

Experimental

Materials :

7075-T6 aluminum alloy sheets were used as corrosion test metal. Their composition was Cu 1.2-2.0%, Mg 2.1-2.9%, Mn 0.3%, Fe 0.5%, Si 0.4%, Zn 5.1-6.1%, Ti 0.2%, Cr 0.18-0.28% and Al was the margin. Alkaline solutions of different concentrations (0.03-0.08 M) were prepared by dissolving sodium hydroxide in water. The purified water was produced by an AKLH-VI-30 special ultrapure water machine.

Test methods :

The size of each 7075-T6 aluminum alloy sheet was approximately 2 × 20 × 50 mm. Each sheet was cleaned with distilled water and then degreased with acetone. After the surface had been dried, the surface area of each sheet was calculated, and the sheets were weighed in an AL104/

01 electronic balance to an accuracy of 0.1 mg. The volume of corrosion test solution was 1.5 L. Each aluminium sheet was hung by non-extruded PTFE-thread and fully immersed in alkaline solution. The corrosion temperature was controlled by either a water bath heating device or a microwave reaction apparatus. The stirring rate was controlled by a JJ-1 constant speed timing electric blender at 80 r/min. The microwave power was set at 300 W. The corrosion temperatures were 45, 55, 65, 75 and 85 °C. The duration of the corrosion test was 6 h. At the end of each corrosion test, each corroded aluminium sheet was rinsed with distilled water and cleaned with a brush. The specimens were then cleaned with ethanol in an ultrasonic bath, dried, and weighed, and the loss in mass due to immersion corrosion was determined. The corrosion rate could be calculated using the following equation :

$$v = \frac{\Delta m}{St}$$

Here, v is the corrosion rate ($\text{g}/\text{m}^2 \text{ h}$), Δm is the loss in weight after the corrosion test (g), S is the surface area of the aluminium sheet (m^2) and t is corrosion time (h).

Results and discussion

Influence of temperature and concentration of alkali on loss of aluminium mass :

Aluminium can corrode easily in sodium hydroxide

solutions. This process gives off plenty of hydrogen. The reaction of aluminium in sodium hydroxide solution can be expressed as follows :

The results of the test are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. Figs. 1A-E show the relationship between the loss of aluminium and the duration of the corrosion process when the temperature was controlled by water bath, Figs. 2A-E show the relationship between the loss of aluminium mass and the duration of corrosion when the test temperature was controlled by microwave heating. These figures show that the loss of aluminium mass increased as temperature and concentration of alkali increased. For the initial stage, when the reaction rate was higher, graphs C, D and E in Figs. 1 and 2 show a higher curve slope for the first three hours. After that, the reaction curve gradually reached a plateau. The two sets of curves representing the relationship between the loss of aluminium mass and the duration of the corrosion process for the two heating processes were consistent with those of other studies. This indicated that, under microwave heating conditions, the corrosion process and mechanism coincided with those in conventional water bath heating conditions. Under microwave heating conditions, the loss of aluminium mass

Fig. 1. Relationship between corrosion time and mass loss of aluminium under water bath heating conditions.

Fig. 2. Relationship between corrosion time and mass loss of aluminium under microwave heating conditions.

was about 33–40% greater (Fig. 3). This indicates that microwave radiation increased the rate of aluminium corrosion in sodium hydroxide solution.

Corrosion kinetics and comparison of rate constant :

The corrosion laws for the process by which aluminium corrodes in acid medium have been reported in literature. These articles have pointed out that the relationship between corrosion rate and acid concentration matched the Mathur formula¹³. The experimental results were ana-

lyzed, and the corrosion kinetics law for the corrosion of aluminium in sodium hydroxide solution was found to differ from that of the corrosion of aluminium in acid medium. The corrosion law of this system may be assumed to be :

$$v = k.c^n \tag{2}$$

Here, v is the corrosion rate ($\text{g/m}^2 \text{ h}$), k is rate constant [$\text{g/m}^2 \text{ h (mol/L)}^{-n}$], c is concentration of sodium hydroxide solution (mol/L), and n is the reaction order. The 1 h corrosion rates of aluminium in sodium hydroxide solutions of different concentrations with water bath heating and microwave heating are shown in Fig. 4A and B. The results (Fig. 4) indicate that the corrosion rate increased as temperature and concentration increased. The corrosion rates obtained from microwave heating were much higher than those obtained with water bath heating. From eq. (2) we have

$$\ln v = \ln k + n \ln c \tag{3}$$

The relationship between $\ln v$ and $\ln c$ is shown in Fig. 5. This indicates that the corrosion laws of aluminium in alkaline solution with different test conditions have a strongly linear relationship as expected from expressions (2) and (3). The expression (2) was used to draw the linear regression curves shown in Fig. 5. The relevant regression parameters are listed in Table 1.

As shown in Table 1, the linear correlation coeffi-

Fig. 3. Difference in loss of aluminium between microwave and water bath heating conditions.

Fig. 4. Corrosion rates.

coefficients of $\ln v$ and $\ln c$ for the two heating methods are both greater than 0.98, and the curves in Fig. 5 show a good linear relationship. This means that the corrosion rate was proportional to the concentration of alkaline solution. The rate constant increased as temperature increased (Table 1). When both the concentration of the corrosion solution and the temperature were held constant, the rate constant obtained from the microwave heating method was generally greater than that obtained from the water

Fig. 5. Relationship between $\ln v$ and $\ln c$ when heated by : (A) water bath and (B) microwave.

bath heating method. This indicates that microwave irradiation can increase the degree of activation of the reaction molecules more effectively than water bath heating. This method can increase the reaction rate and accelerate the corrosion process.

Kinetic parameters :

According to the Arrhenius equation, the relationship between temperature and reaction rate constant is :

Table 1. Linear regression parameters of $\ln v$ and $\ln c$ curves (Fig. 5)

T (°C)	Correlation coefficient		Reaction order (n)		Rate constant (k) [g/m ² h ⁻¹ (mol L ⁻¹) ⁻ⁿ]	
	Water bath	Microwave	Water bath	Microwave	Water bath	Microwave
	45	0.988	0.979	1.11	1.06	1964.51
55	0.989	0.988	1.12	1.07	2617.56	3463.38
65	0.993	0.987	1.16	1.12	3983.83	5943.18
75	0.990	0.989	1.17	1.09	5431.66	6768.27
85	0.993	0.990	1.17	1.09	7115.28	8349.86

Fig. 6. Relationship between $\ln v$ and $1/T$ when heated by : (A) water bath and (B) microwave.

$$\ln v = -E_a/RT + \ln A \quad (4)$$

Here, v is the corrosion rate ($\text{g/m}^2 \text{h}$), E_a is apparent activation energy (kJ/mol), R is the universal gas constant ($\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$), T is temperature (K) and A is the pre-exponential factor ($\text{g/m}^2 \text{h}$). The relationship between $\ln v$ and $1/T$ is shown in Fig. 6. The slope of the line in Fig. 6 can be used to find E_a , and the pre-exponential factor A can be deduced from the linear intercept. The linear re-

gression results of all the curves in Fig. 6 are listed in Table 2. The parameters listed in Table 2 imply that the obtained linear relationship under the two heating methods all had correlation coefficients higher than 0.995. This indicates that the process of aluminium corrosion in sodium hydroxide solution fits the Arrhenius equation. The data in Table 2 imply that the value of apparent activation energy E_a and pre-exponential factor increase as the concentration of the alkaline solution increased. At a given concentration, the value of E_a obtained from microwave heating method was generally lower than that obtained from water bath heating, and the pre-exponential value in case of microwave heating was much higher. As the corrosion of aluminium in sodium hydroxide solution is not an elementary reaction, the apparent activation energy is not the energy requirements of the effective collision between molecules in an elementary reaction. Rather, the value of apparent activation energy E_a indirectly reflects the ability of the corrosion rate to vary with temperature. The pre-exponential tended to increase with increasing concentration of alkaline solution. This indicates that increases in the concentration of sodium hydroxide increase the effective collision frequency of reaction molecules and therefore the reaction rate. All analysis of the kinetic parameters show that microwave irradiation not only provided the required energy for the corrosion reaction but also created a non-thermal effect that promoted the molecular activation of the components and increased the degree of the reaction. This is due to the oscillations of the microwave electric field. Thermal movement alone cannot provide the oriented movement of dipole rearrangement within an electric field, but the oscillation frequency caused by the microwaves can. The

Table 2. Linear regression parameters of $\ln v$ and $1/T$ curves (Fig. 6)

C (mol/L)	Correlation coefficient (r)		Apparent activation energy (E_a) (kJ/mol)		Pre-exponential (A) ($\text{g/m}^2 \text{h}$)	
	Water bath	Microwave	Water bath	Microwave	Water bath	Microwave
0.03	0.995	0.998	23.89	23.34	3.06×10^5	4.22×10^5
0.04	0.999	0.993	24.22	23.58	5.40×10^5	7.15×10^5
0.05	0.998	0.998	24.58	24.17	8.06×10^5	1.15×10^6
0.06	0.999	0.996	25.18	24.78	1.21×10^6	1.58×10^6
0.07	0.998	0.996	25.62	25.41	1.62×10^6	2.28×10^6
0.08	0.999	0.997	26.07	25.77	2.10×10^6	2.96×10^6

rearrangement of polar molecules increased the required geometric probability during the effective collision of reaction molecules, producing a higher pre-exponential. This proved that microwaves could accelerate the corrosion process and increase the corrosion rate.

Conclusion :

The present results may assist research on microwave heating as a tool for accelerating corrosion and may help in proving the efficiency of methods meant to detect the corrosion hazards posed by hazardous chemicals.

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